

Scented Pages: Decoding Smells in *Das Parfum*

S. Ahn, N. al Assali, and N.W. Olenderek

Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

seoyeong.ahn@student.uva.nl / 2832242

n.al.assali@student.vu.nl / 2631076

n.w.olenderek@student.vu.nl / 2671423

Abstract. This paper explores the intersection of digital humanities and sensory history by analysing olfactory references in Patrick Süskind's *Das Parfum* in the context of 18th-century France. Utilising the Odeuropa project's smell extractor tool demo, we extract and examine scent-related words from the novel, mapping them against historical knowledge of the era. We aim to highlight the prevalence and variety of olfactory descriptions by employing digital text analysis to create a word cloud. By correlating these findings with the socioeconomic divisions of the time, we investigate how different social classes are associated with specific scents and their quality, revealing deeper insights into the novel's representation of smell and its social implications. Our analysis reveals a strong correlation between scents and social stratification: the poorer classes are often associated with more negative olfactory descriptions, while the upper classes are linked with more pleasant scents. This differentiation deepens our understanding of the novel's thematic layers and highlights the historical socio-olfactory landscape of 18th-century France. This shows the powerful role of scent in literature as a marker for highlighting social divisions, enriching our understanding of Süskind's narrative technique and the historical context of his work.

Keywords: Digital Humanities, Sensory History, Olfactory Analysis, Socioeconomic Class, Odeuropa, 18th-century France, *Das Parfum*.

1. Introduction

It is impossible to omit Patrick Süskind's *Das Parfum* in a discussion of the intersection of culture and smell, just as it is impossible to disregard the role smells play in our lives (Synnott, 1991). Set in 18th-century pre-revolutionary France, *Das Parfum* contains an abundance of detailed olfactory depictions seen through the eyes of the protagonist, Jean Baptiste Grenouille, who possesses a supernatural sense of smell. He eventually realises he does not emit any kind of odour and creates a variety of human scents throughout his life, inspired by his own specific experiences. It is Grenouille's extraordinary nose that allows him to be more objective in his perception and categorisation of smells. At first, he does not distinguish odours as good or bad; as he furthers his involvement in society, however, he observes the correlations between smells and the places and people that emit them. Following his train of thought, this paper intends to pursue a two-pronged research question; from the humanities perspective, the goal is to evaluate the authenticity of *Das Parfum*'s representation of the interplay between social classes and olfactory experiences in 18th-century France. From the computer science perspective, the intention is to evaluate the practicality and versatility of the Odeuropa extraction tool in the investigation of the relationship between social classes and odours in *Das Parfum* as well as the history of 18th-century Paris. Furthermore, using computational methods to analyse literary and historical sources opens up new research possibilities as well as opportunities to re-examine previously investigated areas of knowledge. Simply using existing technologies to conduct research leads to their development and refinement as they undergo a process of trial and error; this is a reason why even unsuccessful endeavours are a valuable contribution since their faultiness requires evaluation, leading to further improvement of olfactory analysis in the literature field.

2. Dataset

For our project, we analysed a dataset comprising selected excerpts from Patrick Süskind's *Das Parfum*, totalling approximately 3,000 words. These excerpts were manually picked by us and strategically chosen for their rich olfactory descriptions, encompassing a wide range of scents related to characters, locations, and plot developments. This was the best way to handle the processing limit of the Odeuropa smell extractor tool (Streamlit, n.d.) and ensure that the data was accurately divided into separate social classes.

Quantitatively, our dataset included over 200 unique scent-related terms, each categorised according to the type of odour described (e.g., floral, putrid). Prior to analysis, the dataset underwent preprocessing to remove stopwords and disambiguate terms separated by “|” to ensure accuracy, resulting in detailed columns such as ‘Book,’ ‘Smell_Word,’ and ‘Smell_Source,’ among others, to categorise olfactory information. This dataset served as a foundational tool for examining the novel's olfactory landscape and its historical and social implications.

Alain Corbin's *The Foul and the Fragrant* (1982) serves as a primary qualitative resource. Published three years before the novel *Das Parfum*, this book thoroughly investigates the cultural history of fragrance in France, focusing on the perception and use of odours within the social imagination. The qualitative resource gained from this source is important to the study, providing insights into the historical and social settings of olfactory experiences, complemented by additional scholarly articles to deepen our analysis. This comprehensive approach allows us to explore the intersection of scent, society, and narrative in 18th-century France.

The dataset analysed in this study, along with the preprocessing steps and analysis code, is available for review and further research. See the Appendix section for links to the dataset and the documentation.

3. Related Work

The concept of digital humanities has been around for a long time, with reports of its use dating back to the mid-20th century (Sula & Hill, 2017). In the field of digital humanities, the use of computational tools for analysing text has opened up new possibilities for literary studies. One significant work in this area is Jockers' *Macroanalysis: Digital Methods and Literary History* (2013), which introduced the concept of macroanalysis for literature, allowing for the examination of patterns and trends across large datasets of literary texts. This approach has significantly influenced a wide range of subsequent research in digital humanities.

Alongside this, there is growing interest in how literature talks about the senses, especially smell,

which has long been understudied. For example, the book *Aroma: The Cultural History of Smell* by Classen, Howes, and Synnott (1994) looks at how different cultures and times have thought about smell, including in literature. A salient example from this book is the discussion of how, in the 4th century, Christians viewed perfumes and artificial scents with suspicion, associating them with ‘food for demons.’ This belief led them to shun what they regarded as ‘pagan sensuality.’ They even stopped washing regularly, considering the natural body odours as scents assigned by a divine creator, aligning with their religious beliefs (Classen et al., 1994). This historical perspective on smell highlights its complex role in cultural and religious contexts.

Building on such historical and cultural studies of smell, a recent project employing digital tools to extract and analyse olfactory references in literary texts that stands out in this area is by Odeuropa (Van Erp et al., 2023), using AI technology to find and study mentions of smells in old texts and images from European history and displaying the findings in different formats. Their work is relevant because it uses new tools to promote an important but overlooked part of the cultural heritage of Europe’s history. For our project, we are making use of a demo of their tool in order to study and analyse the novel *Das Parfum* and compare it to what we know about life in 18th-century France, especially how smells were different for different social classes.

4. Problem Statement

The analysis of *Das Parfum*’s description of the relationship between social classes and olfactory experiences in 18th-century France raises questions regarding the historical and social fidelity of its depictions. Examining these characteristics entails inherent challenges, requiring research into the formulation of rigorous authenticity criteria. The project employs a systematic strategy to navigate literary works’ inherent fictional nature. As a result, the key humanities question arises: How accurately does *Das Parfum* capture and depict the disparities of social classes and olfactory experiences in the historical setting of 18th-century France?

Exploring this complex relationship indicates the need to employ a variety of computational approaches to analyse the novel and 18th-century Parisian history. The first computational challenge stems from the Odeuropa smell extraction tool’s potential limitations, as its original purpose is to identify mentions of smells and their components (e.g. ‘stank,’ ‘odour,’ ‘scent’) for each smell source in the Odeuropa Smell Explorer, whereas our project’s focus is on smell sources’ ‘locations’ and ‘odour carriers.’ Furthermore, due to issues with the tools’ formatting, we needed to do some data clean-up to be able to conduct our analyses.

Another challenge is determining the most effective visualisation that can show intersecting words that both appear in the word clouds of each rich and poor generated by the preprocessed dataset. This yields the key computational question: How do we analyse the intricate interplay between social classes and odours in *Das Parfum* and 18th-century Paris by utilising computational tools?

We performed an in-depth investigation of both computational limitations and evaluative strategies, fostering a thorough comprehension of the complex interaction between computational tools and the authenticity evaluation of literary depictions.

5. Method/Approach

For our research, we manually selected excerpts from the novel that are rich in olfactory descriptions. We then employed the Odeuropa extractor tool demo to systematically extract scent-related words from *Das Parfum*. The extracted data is then processed using R for preprocessing. This includes tokenisation of words and eliminating punctuation and stopwords. We further used Rstudio and Python to create visual representations of our findings, including word clouds and Venn diagrams, to illustrate the frequency and contextual usage of scent-related words across different social strata depicted in the literature.

5.1 Preprocessing

We began our research with the Odeuropa extraction tool demo, an effective technology developed to extract scent-related words. While this tool produced useful olfactory information, more preprocessing in R was required to fit the data to our research objectives. Preliminary data preprocessing was completed using R. This involved dealing with missing values, tokenising words, deleting stopwords, and removing punctuation to ensure the data’s quality and relevancy. To improve our dataset for word cloud generation, we addressed the concatenation challenges

given by the Odeuropa program. We processed the dataset with R and Python, adding new rows for each smell source and removing vertical bars to ensure correct illustration.

After the initial import and cleaning of the dataset in R, we applied specific preprocessing rules tailored to our dataset's needs. In the rich dataset, we encountered inconsistencies with the words 'oils' and 'oil.' To maintain consistency in our analysis, we implemented a rule to replace 'oils' with 'oil.' This selective stemming was necessary because applying a full stemming process to the entire dataset altered the values inaccurately, affecting the correctness of our data.

For the poor dataset, we identified the word 'like' as a recurrent issue, which was inaccurately picked up by the Odeuropa extractor as a smell source. Since this problem was unique to this dataset, we added 'like' to our custom list of stopwords for removal in the preprocessing phase. This step ensured that this irrelevant word would not skew our analysis.

These dataset-specific modifications complement the general preprocessing steps of data cleaning, indexing, tokenisation, stopwords removal, and punctuation elimination. By tailoring our process to the unique characteristics of each dataset, we ensured more accurate and relevant analysis results.

5.2 Solution approach and design

Our solution approach involved a multi-step pipeline designed to analyse olfactory descriptions within *Das Parfum*. Initially, we employed close reading to select extracts with relevant scent references. These selections were then processed through the Odeuropa smell extraction tool, generating a structured dataset. Our analysis combined quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods. Statistical tests identified patterns in scent descriptions and their relation to social divisions, while visualisations helped illustrate these findings. Lastly, qualitative insights from historical texts will be used. This integrated method allowed us to delve deeply into the socio-olfactory landscape of 18th-century France, leveraging both literary and historical perspectives to enrich our understanding of olfactory representations in the novel.

5.2.1 Data Visualization: Word Cloud, Venn Diagram, and Frequency Tables

First, we formulated word clouds to visually depict the olfactory terms linked with various socioeconomic groups in *Das Parfum*, providing qualitative insights into Süskind's socio-olfactory narrative. Then, using Venn diagrams, we identified connections in olfactory senses between rich and poor people, bridging social divides. Finally, we did the quantitative analysis using frequency tables, which provided a deeper comprehension of the prevalence of distinct olfactory words within each social class.

5.3 Evaluation Setup

To evaluate our findings, we will be using both qualitative and quantitative methods. In quantitative analysis, we will be utilising the Chi-squared test, which is a statistical test, to examine the relationship between olfactory descriptions and socioeconomic status. We will focus on determining the significance of the results based on metrics like p-values and chi-square values. On the other hand, qualitative analysis will involve evaluating the context of olfactory references in *Das Parfum* and their effect on the story's socio-olfactory landscape. We will analyse the accuracy of these references and their impact on the narrative and historical context. The dual approach will help us gain a more comprehensive understanding of the role that olfactory elements play in the novel and how they reflect 18th-century societal norms.

6. Results

In this section, we describe and evaluate the results of our quantitative investigation of the social classification of the smellscape of Patrick Süskind's *Das Parfum*. To decode and interpret the novel's description of the complex relationship between social classes and olfactory senses, we used quantitative methods, including the Odeuropa extraction tool and R for data preprocessing and R for data visualisation.

6.1 Smell Word Clouds

We created smell word clouds to illustrate the frequency and significance of olfactory terms linked with different socioeconomic classes in *Das Parfum*. The word clouds present the distinguished olfactory senses of the novel's rich and poor characters. Smell terms including 'stank,' 'stench,' 'smelled,' and 'stinking' were used for the poor, while 'smelled,' 'odours,' 'perfume,' 'scent,' and 'aromatic' were used for the wealthy.

Fig.1. Poor Smell Word Cloud

Fig.2. Rich Smell Word Cloud

6.2 Venn Diagram: Identifying Common Olfactory Ground

To identify shared olfactory senses, we employed Venn diagrams to depict intersecting smell source terms found in three groups of people, including rich, poor, and 'human in general.' This analytical approach sought to discover commonality in smell sources across social classes.

Fig.3. Venn Diagram Showing the Intersection of Smell Sources Description between the Rich, Poor, and General Human Smell

The intersection of words suggests shared olfactory words across social strata, challenging the notion of exclusive scent connections. Our findings in this area help us understand how Süskind navigates olfactory complexities to produce a narrative that transcends societal barriers, as well as how 18th-century France shared odours that transcended socio-economic divides. The smell source words 'damp,' 'vinegar,' and 'water' intersect between the poor and rich groups, while the words 'myrrh,' 'incense,' and 'sweat' intersect with every group.

6.3 Frequency Tables: Quantifying Olfactory Narratives

Quantitative analysis of olfactory word frequencies corroborated our qualitative findings. Frequency tables were created to demonstrate the predominance of various olfactory terms within each socioeconomic class, providing a deeper comprehension of the relevance of certain odours in the novel.

Fig.4. Top 20 Smell Sources and their Frequencies in Poor, Rich, and Human in General Categories

The rich group’s highest frequency was the smell source ‘oil’ (6 times), while the poor group’s highest frequency was the word ‘sweat’ (4 times). The group ‘humans in general’ did not have a distinct smell source word, as each of the words ‘milk,’ ‘wood,’ ‘fresh,’ and ‘watery’ was mentioned twice. The smell source word with the highest frequency across all groups is ‘sweat,’ with a total frequency of seven, four by the poor group, two by the rich group, and one by the ‘humans in general’ group. All three groups mentioned the words ‘sweat,’ ‘incense’ (1 time by each group), and ‘myrrh’ (1 time by each group).

6.4 Statistical Testing

	poor	rich
negative	27	4
positive	5	30

Fig.5. Contingency Table for Chi-Test

```
Pearson's Chi-squared test with Yates' continuity correction
data: contingency_table
X-squared = 32.039, df = 1, p-value = 1.511e-08
```

Fig.6. Chi-Test Result

A Chi-squared test conducted in RStudio revealed a significant association between smell source quality (negative vs. positive) and socioeconomic status (poor vs. rich), with a chi-square value of 32.039, degrees of freedom = 1, and a sample size of 66, resulting in a p-value of approximately 1.511e-08. This highly significant p-value, well below the 0.05 alpha level threshold, led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating a strong correlation where negative smells are more frequently associated with lower socioeconomic status and positive smells with higher socioeconomic status.

6.5 Evaluation

For the quantitative evaluation, we conducted the Chi-Squared test to determine how well our research addresses the humanities research question, i.e. “How accurately does *Das Parfum* capture and depict the disparities of social classes and olfactory experiences in the historical setting of 18th-century France?” The results demonstrated a remarkably significant p-value, confirming a strong correlation between olfactory sources and social classes. This statistical analysis validated our qualitative findings, providing significant support for the interconnection of olfactory depictions and social class disparities in the novel.

Our qualitative evaluation involves how the olfactory references were used to ensure that they were accurate to historical events and the novel’s socio-olfactory setting by comparing it with academic literature. For example, scenes in which the protagonist, Jean Baptiste Grenouille, smells the underlying filthy odours of the rich despite their attempts to conceal them with perfumes are consistent with historical practices of limited hygiene among the upper classes in 18th-century France. In fact, in 18th-century France, the bourgeois rarely bathed once a month or washed their hair (Corbin, 2016, p. 278). The precision of these depictions contributes to the novel’s authenticity in representing the olfactory experiences of the time.

In conclusion, our quantitative and qualitative evaluations support the novel’s adherence to historical and social contexts as well as highlight the complex interplay between olfactory descriptions and societal disparities. *Das Parfum* stands out not only as a work of fiction but also as a subtle depiction of the olfactory nuances that reflected the established social fabric of 18th-century France.

7. Discussions and Conclusion

7.1 Discussion

Studying articles and literature about 18th-century France helped us better understand our results and provided valuable insights into the role of smell in that era. In *Das Parfum*, olfactory references are not just narrative tools but also provide a glimpse into the socio-olfactory dynamics of the time. Our analysis showed a clear link between the quality of olfactory descriptions and social class. The poor often had unpleasant body odours, and the rich, fearing the odours emanating from the lower classes (Corbin, 2016, p. 232), could mask theirs with perfumes and other fragrances (Corbin, 2016, p. 276). This demonstrates an olfactory revolution associated with the French bourgeois and higher classes (Brant, 2004). The third division we made, of a human scent, described by the protagonist Grenouille, shows a mix of good and bad smells. It is understood that Grenouille uses the foul smell sources in his creation of a human perfume as the base, as to him, every human smells like “... a sweaty-oily, sour-cheesy, quite richly repulsive basic theme that clung to all humans equally ...” (Süskind, 1987, p. 59). Those scents combined reminded him of the poor places where he was born and raised. He then used the fresh scents to mask it, giving it as close to a general scent as what he considered a human.

The rich social class's olfactory sources included floral words such as “tuberose,” “jasmine,” “rose,” “jonquil flowers,” and “lily.” Indeed, among the bourgeoisie, it was fashionable to decorate homes and greenhouses with flowers like tuberose, jasmine, golden stock flowers, and forget-me-nots (Corbin, 2016, p. 300). One of the words that had high frequency includes “leather,” which can be related to French women’s use of perfumed gloves and animal skins to disguise signs of ageing and protect themselves against diseases (Muchembled, 2020).

In fact, in eighteenth-century France, smell was closely tied with hygiene, with unpleasant smells regarded as a health risk and pleasant fragrances considered to be devices for warding off deadly illnesses. During the plague, doctors used French-designed costumes, including a peak containing herbs and fragrances, that they believed would prevent the spread of the plague. However, the costume was only effective in repelling fleas carrying the bacterium (Mant, 2023). The smell emerging from the proletariat disgusted and terrified the bourgeoisie. The bourgeoisie frequently complained about smells emanating from the proletarians labouring in their kitchens. Being one of the highest frequency smell sources in poor social class, “kitchen” included smells from exposed trash cans beneath the kitchen sink, the musty odour of detergent, and the smell of the vent (Corbin, 2016, p. 259).

Despite the bourgeoisie's hatred for the odours emanating from the proletariat, paradoxically, In *Das Parfum*, the protagonist Grenouille can still smell the underlying foul scents of the rich, which is historically accurate. High-class French citizens seldom bathed; instead, they only washed their

hands and faces and changed their underclothes to maintain a superficial level of cleanliness (Elmarsy, 2020). That would explain sweat being a common smell among the French people from all classes.

The myrrh and incense, also common words in our three divisions, show that humans from all classes had something in common: going to church. Myrrh holds importance to Christians as it was one of the gifts given after the birth of Jesus (New International Version, Matthew 2:11). The practice of lighting incense in churches is believed to date back to the 5th century. Using it as a sacrifice was looked down upon by many Christians as a pagan ritual, but its use to drive away diseases and illnesses is what kept it a popular practice amongst most Christians and churches (Caseau, 2014).

These reports support our findings, indicating a clear correlation between the olfactory descriptions in the novel and the socioeconomic class distinctions of the time. Both reflect historical practices and beliefs about scent, cleanliness, and disease prevention.

Our results, therefore, fit into the picture of the socioeconomic state of France in the 18th century by exploring an aspect that has yet to be researched enough: the olfactory experience. Our quantitative results, on the one hand, confirm our hypothesis that there is a clear distinction between the social classes. Our qualitative analysis, on the other hand, further confirms that the author did their work in researching the socioeconomic and olfactory state of France in the 18th century.

For our analysis, we utilised the smell extractor tool provided by the Odeuropa project. Using Rstudio, we applied a digital text analysis methodology to identify and categorise olfactory references in *Das Parfum*. This approach enabled us to quantitatively evaluate the frequency and context of scent-related words throughout the novel.

A significant limitation of our method was the reliance on selected excerpts from Süskind's novel rather than analysing the entire text. This selection process, necessitated by the smell extractor tool's 1000-word processing limit, may have introduced bias and potentially limited the breadth of our findings. This approach, while practical, shows the need for methodological advancements to accommodate comprehensive textual analysis without compromising the depth of data collected.

Acknowledging the challenges encountered with the smell extractor tool is also crucial. Despite the tool's innovative application, it sometimes generated incorrect data, amalgamated multiple values into a single row using a “|” separator, and incorrectly matched values across columns. Additionally, the tool's inclusion of stopwords as values posed a significant challenge for us, necessitating our team's manual review and extra processing steps to ensure the data's relevance and accuracy. These limitations showed the importance of human oversight in digital text analysis and emphasised areas for future improvement in automated data extraction techniques. Nevertheless, although our analysis method was specifically designed for Süskind's novel, it can be applied to other literature with slight tweaks and changes. Further uncovering unexplored realities behind works of fiction.

In future research, we would aim to enhance the smell extractor tool to process larger texts and improve its accuracy for our studies. This ambitious task would require significant effort, focusing our time primarily on refining the tool. Such improvements would enable a comprehensive analysis of olfactory descriptions across various literary works from the same period, facilitating a comparative study. By generating more reliable datasets, we can better assess the historical authenticity of authors' sensory descriptions. This effort will highlight the value of digital humanities in exploring sensory experiences and literary analysis, opening new paths for understanding literature's sensory dimensions and social implications.

7.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, our research has answered both of our research questions. Firstly, we have concluded that *Das Parfum* is an accurate depiction of the disparities between social classes and the olfactory experience of life in 18th-century France. The distinction between rich and poor is evident in the smell quality, carrier, and source, which we verified in academic literature based on historical sources (Brant, 2004; Corbin, 1986; Elmarsy, 2022; Muchembled, 2020). Secondly, we have gained experience in using computational methods—namely the Odeuropa extraction tool—to analyse the relationship between class and odour in *Das Parfum*. As the Odeuropa tool was a demo version, we encountered some erroneous inconsistencies that required further processing and refining; learning from this experience, a possibility of modifying and improving the Odeuropa extraction tool arises. Furthermore, such a development would enable us to expand the project in the sphere of olfactory analysis in literature.

References

1. Brant, C. (2004). *Fume and Perfume: Some Eighteenth-Century Uses of Smell*. *Journal of British Studies*, 43(4), 444–463. <https://doi.org/10.1086/421927>
2. Caseau, B. (2014). *From House to Church: The Introduction of Incense*. Sorbonne-fr. https://www.academia.edu/494438/From_house_to_church_the_introduction_of_incense
3. Classen, C., Howes, D., & Synnott, A. (1994). *Aroma: The Cultural History of Smell*. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA24054369>
4. Corbin, Alain. (2016). *The Foul and the Fragrant: Odor and the French Social Imagination* (N, Joo, Trans.). Publishing house OROT. (1982).
5. Elmasry, F. (2020, April 22). *Historian Explores the Evolution of Personal Hygiene*. *Voice of America*. https://www.voanews.com/a/science-health_historian-explores-evolution-personal-hygiene/6187950.html
6. Jockers, M. L. (2013). *Macroanalysis: Digital Methods and Literary History*. University of Illinois Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5406/j.ctt2jcc3m>
7. Mant, M. (2020, May 15). *Behind the Beak: Plague Doctor Iconography in 2020*. S Y N a P S I S. <https://medicalhealthhumanities.com/2020/05/15/behind-the-beak-plague-doctor-iconography-in-2020/#:~:text=The%20beak%20of%20the%20Plague>
8. Muchembled, R. (2020). *Smells: A Cultural History of Odours in Early Modern Times*. John Wiley & Sons.
9. Streamlit. (n.d.). <https://smell-extractor.tools.eurecom.fr/>
10. Sula, C. A., & Hill, H. (2017). *The Early History of Digital Humanities*. DH. <https://dh2017.adho.org/abstracts/347/347.pdf>
11. Süskind, P. (1987). *Perfume: The Story of a Murderer*. <https://www.pairfum.com/documents/Perfume-Patrick-Suskind-The-Story-Of-Murderer.pdf>
12. Synnott, A. (1991), *A Sociology of Smell*. *Canadian Review of Sociology/Revue canadienne de sociologie*, 28: 437-459. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-618X.1991.tb00164.x>
13. Van Erp, M., Tullett, W., Christlein, V., Ehrhart, T., Hüriyyetoğlu, A., Leemans, I., Lisena, P., Menini, S., Schwabe, D., Tonelli, S., Troncy, R., & Zinnen, M. (2023). *More than the Name of the Rose*. *The American Historical Review*, 128(1), 335–369. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/rhad141>

Appendix:

Link to Github including raw data, processed data, preprocessing and visualisation code and visualisations: <https://github.com/Nour-alasali/DHSAIP.git>